

CUSTOMER SATISFACTION AND LOYALTY SURVEY @ FYNSEA LINES & LOGISTICS

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Abstract:

A multitude of companies today has already identified the need to create a loyal customer base and acknowledges that maintaining existing customers and extending business with them is significantly less expensive than acquiring new customers. Empirical proof of the proliferation of such customer loyalty efforts in the business world is e.g. provided in the form of loyalty programs, which many companies have installed during the past years. By engaging in efforts aimed at creating customer loyalty, which in turn fosters financial success in monetary terms firms react to increasing competitive challenges. Within this study, four relational characteristics were examined. In addition, analyses were conducted for a multitude of other contingency factors that are not included in the present study. Overall, however, no conclusive moderations were identified. Nevertheless, it may be assumed that customer diversity still has moderating effects on the formation of customer loyalty. The determinants contained in this study, however, capture rather general evaluations of relationships between LSPs and their customers, which may be too broad to be subject to moderating effects. For this reason it would be sensible to examine antecedents of the employed determinants, as moderating effects could surface when this level of detail is added to the analyses.

Key Words: Customer Satisfaction, FYNSEA lines & Logistics

Introduction:

Within research, the investigation of customer loyalty gained importance when the classic marketing paradigm with its instrumental and transactional orientation proved unsuitable in the context of longer-term business relationships. Instead, the relationship marketing approach, which is specifically concerned with the study of relational ex-changes, gained importance within research, serving as a conceptual foundation for the majority of customer loyalty researchers. The question of how loyalty develops has been subject to an abundance of research, leading to an expansive body of literature on loyalty determinants. The extant literature exploring different factors and their constituent effects on loyalty, however, reveals a strong focus on consumer goods and industrial equipment settings, while industrial services have received relatively little attention so far. In addition, the majority of articles incorporates merely a few potential determinants and thus fails to draw a comprehensive picture of the mechanisms of customer loyalty formation.

Just like other businesses, logistics service providers (LSPs) are faced with increasing competitive pressure that urges them to concentrate not only on operational business processes, but also on an efficient and effective customer management. In the US alone, LSPs' revenues grew from US-\$ 31 billion in 1995 to US-\$ 85 billion in 2004 and logistics outsourcing expenditures as a fraction of total logistics expenditures are at over 40% and expected to rise even further. One way to meet this challenge of rapid growth and expansion, according to Langley et al. is to focus on establishing, maintaining, and developing relationships with customers. An often proposed driver of logistics outsourcing is the need to develop and maintain competitive advantage, which customers of LSPs intend to achieve through concentrating on core competencies and re-engineering. Another important driver is the ongoing globalization, which several authors regard as the most important challenge that companies are facing. In this context, LSPs can play an important role as facilitators of global trade. Along with globalization, however, companies that outsource logistics activities increasingly try to consolidate the number of LSPs they use globally. Therefore, LSPs do not only have to devise sustain-able growth strategies, but also have to develop intercultural management competencies, a challenge hardly addressed in LSP management literature.

While intercultural management deals with the influence of culture on management styles in different countries, it is also arguable whether a one best way management paradigm is applicable even within national confines. LSPs' customers are extremely diverse and similarly, relationships between LSPs and their customers can be expected to exhibit momentous differences. As such, it is a crucial management issue for LSPs to de-sign their customer loyalty efforts in a manner that accounts for both cultural context and different relationship characteristics.

Research Goals:

As outlined in the preceding section, LSPs are confronted with diverse management challenges that result from continuous growth, globalization, and customer diversity. The aim of the present study therefore is to identify determinants of customer loyalty in relationships between LSPs and their customers by explicitly considering different characteristics and cultural contexts of such relationships. In this sense, the present research is positioned at the interface of marketing and logistics and is intended to contribute not only to logistics research, but also to research in marketing, customer loyalty, and cultural studies. In order to address the concept of customer loyalty, it is important to understand the mechanisms underlying loyalty in the logistics outsourcing context. For this reason, the starting point of the present research will be the study of Wallenburg, who studied customer loyalty within relationships between LSPs and their customers. On this basis, factors that can be surmised to determine customer loyalty in such relationships will be proposed and interdependencies between these factors will be identified. The resulting comprehensive explanatory model of customer loyalty will not only provide insights into the constitution of customer loyalty, but will also serve as the basis for subsequent analyses.

As stated previously, a globalizing marketplace and the need of LSPs to render logistics services on an international scale requires intercultural management competencies. Before being able to apply such management techniques, though, a thorough understanding of cultural differences between different countries is necessary. The present study will therefore provide a starting point for such analyses by investigating cultural differences between two important markets for logistics outsourcing, the USA and Germany. Particular differences between Germany and the USA will be identified and applied to the previously devised customer loyalty model. As a result, differences between the two countries with respect to the formation of customer loyalty can be inferred. Finally, this study will investigate in how far different relationship conditions influence the development of customer loyalty. For this purpose, important relationship characteristics will be identified and their moderating influences on the customer loyalty model will be examined. This will provide information on the robustness of the customer loyalty model versus relational contingencies and will suggest if it is necessary to differentiate customer loyalty efforts accordingly.

Customer Satisfaction:

The term logistics is often misinterpreted to mean transportation. In fact, the scope of logistics goes well beyond transportation. Logistics forms the system that ensures the delivery of the product in the entire supply pipeline. This includes transportation, packaging, storage and handling methods, and information flow. The impact of logistics in the ability of a company to satisfy its customers cannot be overstated. All other efforts at modernization within a company would not bear fruit until the logistics system is carefully designed to facilitate the smooth and efficient flow of goods in the system.

The topic of logistics is relatively new in India. There have been some companies that have done work in this area, but a large number of companies are only now beginning to realize the benefits of designing and managing the entire supply chain. With India joining the global marketplace, the role of logistics assumes greater importance.

The industrial policies in India have prompted manufacturers to build plants in remote, backward areas due to inexpensive land and tax benefits. This poses some serious logistical problems. Apart from a poor road and transportation network, the existing communications system in India leaves a lot to be desired by any international standard. It is in this context that logistics has to be considered in India.

Objective of the Study:

- ✓ A study on customer level of satisfaction in towards FYNSEA Lines & Logistics
- ✓ To identify the loyalty of customer towards FYNSEA Lines & Logistics
- ✓ To measure the specific reasons for satisfaction and dissatisfaction in with FYNSEA Lines & Logistics.
- ✓ To identify the recommendations of FYNSEA Lines & Logistics to others by existing loyal customers.

Scope of the Study:

- ✓ Scope of the study mainly to know the current level of customer satisfaction.
- ✓ Scope of the study mainly to know the loyalty of the customer towards the company.
- ✓ To give suggestion regarding improvement of performance standard of the Company
- ✓ To inform the management about current level.

Limitations of the Study:

- ✓ Time limit restricts detailed survey work for this particular topic of research.
- ✓ The survey is restricted to the customers of FYNSEA Lines & Logistics who are involved in imports.
- ✓ Some customers have lack of time, so they may not communicate properly.

Research Methodology:

The objective of the study has been achieved by using both Primary and Secondary Data's. The data's obtained for the study was primarily from field investigation carried out among the customers of FYNSEA Lines & Logistics.

Sampling:

Sample design is a definite plan for obtaining a sample from a given population. It refers to the technique or the procedure the researcher would adopt in selecting items for samples. Samples are studied for the population who are the customers of FYNSEA Lines & Logistics. Research design is needed because it facilitates the smooth railing of the various research operations thereby making research as effective as possible yielding maximal information with minimal expenditure of effort, time and money.

Sample Size:

The Customers, to whom FYNSEA Lines & Logistics provides service is taken into consideration. The sample size is 85.

Primary Data:

Primary data was collected through Online Survey. The methods followed for the analysis and interpretation of data are: Univariate Percentage Analysis and Weighted average method.

Analysis and Interpretation:

Overall Experience to Access Ability and Responses (of FYNSEA Lines & Logistics):

Interpretation:

Out of the total respondents, overall experience to access ability and responses is 35% have suggested Excellent, 20% as Very Good, 40% as Good and remaining 5% as fair.

Representative's Ability to Help You Resolve Issue/Need:

Interpretation:

Out of the total responses, it shows that the representative ability to help resolve the issue/need in which 10% have suggested as Excellent, 45% as Very Good, 40% as Good and remaining 5% as poor.

Courteousness and Helpfulness of Representatives:

Interpretation:

Out of the total responses, the representative on being courteous & helpfulness for 15% have rated as Excellent, 45% as Very Good and 40% as Good.

Rank Correlations Table:

	Score	Rank
Overall Experience	35%	1
Representative ability	10%	4
Courteous & helpfulness	15%	3
Overall Experience with Clearance Department	25%	2
Overall Experience on the Shipment Delivery	15%	3

Interpretation:

From the above table it shows that the respondents have ranked the overall experience as first, overall experience with clearance department as second rank, courteous & helpfulness and shipment delivery which is given as third rank and representative ability which is given as fourth rank.

Findings:

- ✓ Out of the total responses, overall experience to access ability and responses is 35% have suggested Excellent, 20% as Very Good, 40% as Good remaining 5% as fair.
- ✓ Out of the total responses, it shows that the representative ability to help resolve the issue/need in which 10% have suggested as Excellent, 45% as Very Good, 40% as Good and remaining 5% as poor.
- ✓ Out of the total responses, the representative on being courteous & helpfulness for 15% have rated as Excellent, 45% as Very Good and 40% as Good.
- ✓ Out of the total responses, Customers Overall experience with FYNSEA Lines & Logistics Clearance Department 25% have rated as Excellent, 35% as Very Good and 35% as Good.
- ✓ Out of the total responses, Customer Overall experience with FYNSEA Shipment Delivery at doorstep 15% have suggested Excellent, 35% as Very Good and 45% are Good.
- ✓ Out of the total responses, 45% prefer Customer Service, 30% feel that the service is Secure, 15% prefer Safety aspect and 10% prefer it due to on time delivery.
- ✓ 25% of the total respondents have more than 10 years of association with FYNSEA Logistics. 10% of the respondents have 7 to 10 years of association, 10% have 5 to 7 years of association and 50% have less than 3 years of association.

Suggestions:

- ✓ Communicate. Whether it is an email newsletter, monthly flier, a reminder card for a tune up, or a holiday greeting card, reach out to your steady customers.
- ✓ Customer Service. Go the extra distance and meet customer needs. Train the staff to do the same.
- ✓ Customers remember being treated well.
- ✓ Employee Loyalty. Loyalty works from the top down. If you are loyal to your employees, they will feel positively about their jobs and pass that loyalty along to your customers.
- ✓ Employee Training. Train employees in the manner that you want them to interact with customers.
- ✓ Empower employees to make decisions that benefit the customer.
- ✓ Customer Incentives. Give customers a reason to return to your business. For instance, because children outgrow shoes quickly, the owner of a children's shoe store might offer a card that makes the tenth pair of shoes half price. Likewise, a dentist may give a free cleaning to anyone who has seen him regularly for five years.
- ✓ Product Awareness. Know what your steady patrons purchase and keep these items in stock. Add other products and/or services that accompany or compliment the products that your regular customers buy regularly. And make sure that your staff understands everything they can about your products.
- ✓ Reliability. If you say a purchase will arrive on Wednesday, deliver it on Wednesday. Be reliable. If something goes wrong, let customers know immediately and compensate them for their inconvenience.
- ✓ Be Flexible. Try to solve customer problems or complaints to the best of your ability. Excuses — such as "That's our policy" — will lose more customers than setting the store on fire.
- ✓ People over Technology. The harder it is for a customer to speak to a human being when he or she has a problem, the less likely it is that you will see that customer again.
- ✓ Know Their Names. Remember the theme song to the television show *Cheer?* Get to know the names of regular customers or at least recognize their faces.

Conclusion:

In addition to suggestions and findings, this study also provides several scopes for further research, which will be addressed in the following paragraphs:

- ✓ While the customer loyalty model validated in this study possesses good power for explaining repurchase intentions and referral behavior, only partial explanation of the construct of additional purchase intentions is achieved. As stated before, factors not contained in the model such as strategic

outsourcing considerations can be assumed to affect the intention of customers to outsource additional logistics activities to the currently most important LSP. For this reason, future studies should explore additional determinants of this loyalty dimension.

- ✓ Measurement model assessment revealed that the operationalizations of fairness in this study does not achieve sufficient discriminance from other constructs, especially from trust and relational satisfaction. As there is a strong theoretical indication that fairness is important in customer loyalty considerations, further studies should modify fairness' measurement model, e.g. by more strongly recurring to the concept of inequity.
- ✓ Within this study, four relational characteristics were examined. In addition, analyses were conducted for a multitude of other contingency factors that are not included in the present study. Overall, however, no conclusive moderations were identified. Nevertheless, it may be assumed that customer diversity still has moderating effects on the formation of customer loyalty. The determinants contained in this study, however, capture rather general evaluations of relationships between LSPs and their customers, which may be too broad to be subject to moderating effects. For this reason it would be sensible to examine antecedents of the employed determinants, as moderating effects could surface when this level of detail is added to the analyses.

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